

INFLUENCE OF SEASONAL VARIATION ON THE ANTIOXIDANT EFFICACY OF INDIAN PROPOLIS

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Abstract

Propolis, a sticky, gummy, balsamic resinous substance fashioned by the honeybees (*Apis mellifera* L.) from the buds or exudates of various plant sources, is a common ingredient used in apitherapy in various parts of the world. It is one of the few natural products that maintained reputation for a long time in food and pharmaceutical industries. Several studies performed on various samples of evidenced that the main secondary metabolites are phenolic substances especially flavonoids, belonging to different sub-classes such as flavanones, flavones, flavonols and dihydroflavonols, which constitute more than 50% of the total propolis weight. Plant source, regional vegetation, seasons of harvesting, geography, type of bee flora, climate changes, physiochemical properties and antimicrobial activity are vital parameters that determine the quality of the propolis. Several reports are available in the literature evidencing the antioxidant, antiplatelet, anticancer, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and hepato-protective nature of propolis. The present study is aimed to determine the effect of seasonal variation on the levels of flavonoid and phenolic content and the anti-oxidant potential of the propolis collected three times during the year 2024, in the spring (April to June), summer (July to September) and fall (October to December) covering over a period of one year. The total phenolic and flavonoid content of propolis extract was found to be relatively higher in samples collected during summer and consequently the free radical scavenging capacity was also found to be increased in the sample.

Keywords: Indian Propolis, Total phenolic content, Total flavonoid content, Free radicals, Anti-oxidant Properties.

Introduction

Over the years, numerous medicaments have been incorporated from holistic remedies into contemporary medicine and the present world is persistently astonishing with expanded natural compounds that can be the gifted sources for the discovery of new drugs vital to medicine. The National Institute of Health (NIH) after extensive research over the last several decades stated that a diet rich in fruits and green vegetables can reduce the onset of several dreadful human ailments [1]. In fact, almost 70% of all drugs currently approved by the U. S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of various primary and secondary human ailments were distillations, combinations, reproductions, or variations of substances that are originally identified from natural sources and their demand is increasing exponentially due to the growing recognition of natural products as being non-toxic, more efficacious, available, accessible and affordable [2]. Hippocrates commented almost 25 centuries ago that “Let food be thy medicine and medicine be thy food”. This admonition parallels that common American saying “you are what you eat”, and the recommendation from the NIH to consume as many as “eight servings of fruits and vegetables a day” to avert common dis-eases. This citation raises a scientific illumination of what components in food are responsible for prevention of diseases and how they act.

Phytochemicals are ecologically derived secondary metabolites synthesized by the plants to protect themselves against damage due to environmental stress such as extreme cold, high temperature, UV radiation and microbial invasions [3, 4]. Astonishingly, these plant derived molecules are reported to have both beneficial and pharmacological properties in alleviating most of the human diseases [5, 6]. Compared to humans, plants have highly developed protective systems due to their sessile nature and hence they serve as a rich source of novel substances for therapeutic applications [7, 8]. Modern medicine is referred to as “evidence-based medicine”, which ensures the safety and efficacy of the herbal or natural products, standardization and development of processing aspects for successful therapeutic applications. The use of natural products as an essential means to new pharmaceutical leads is continually intensifying and is a research field of immense interest because the different structural range of natural compounds can provide lead molecules for therapeutic application based on rationalized molecular modifications[9,10]. Our ancestors recommended some of the natural products, which are

profusely found in nature long before their medicinal values are established scientifically and their golden words are fulfilled by means of current scientific achievements.

Propolis, a sticky, gummy, balsamic resinous substance fashioned by the honeybees (*Apis mellifera* L.) from the buds or exudates of various plant sources, is common ingredient used in apitherapy in various parts of the world. It is stated that propolis use dates back to ancient times, at least to 300BC, where it was used in folk medicine and other activities in many parts of the world [11, 12]. It is one of the few natural products that maintained reputation for a long time in food and pharmaceutical industries [13, 14]. Propolis is a natural product that honeybees collect from several plants and mix it with beeswax and salivary enzymes [15, 16]. The term “propolis” derives from two terms of Greek origin, “pro” and “polis which literally mean “in front of or at the entrance of the city” [17, 18]. Propolis is commonly used by the bees as building material and sealer by maintaining thermal homeostasis, waterproofing of the hive against moisture, reducing vibrations, averting the uncontrolled airflow into the nest, defend the colony against microbial infection and prevent putrefaction [19,20].

Propolis is a lipophilic material melting at temperatures around 70⁰ C [21]. It consists of granules of various sizes and with an enjoyable aromatic smell and different coloration, including red, brown, yellow and light green among others [22-24]. Plant source, regional vegetation, seasons of harvesting, geography, type of bee flora, climate changes, physiochemical properties and antimicrobial activity are vital parameters that determine the quality of the propolis [25,26]. Ethanol is the best suitable solvent to extract the active principals from the propolis but is also used methanol, chloroform, ether and acetone [27-29]. According to a recent report, up to about 300 different components have been isolated, identified from propolis [30-34].

In addition, some non-phenolic compounds belonging to different classes such as aliphatic acids, coumarins, aromatic hydrocarbons, terpenoids, steroids, esters, ketones, aldehydes, fattyacids, aminoacids, polysaccharides, hydrocarbons, hydroxybenzene and isoprenylated benzophenones have also been reported [35- 38]. Further, propolis is a rich source of trace elements such as zinc, manganese, copper, nickel, calcium, iron, silver, vanadium and vitamin B, C, and E [39, 40]. Despite propolis popularity over time, it is not considered as a therapeutic agent in conventional medicinal system as the standardization of chemical composition and biological activities due to diversification of chemical composition are lacking and such

consistency is indispensable for acceptable in the health system. Thus characterization of different types of propolis according to its origin, chemical composition and biological activity is essential. Several reports are available in the literature evidencing the antioxidant, antiplatelet, anticancer, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and hepato-protective nature of propolis [41].

India is one of the largest countries in terms of environmental biodiversity, inhabiting large number of flora and fauna. The various climatic conditions and seasonal variations impart the qualitative and quantitative chemical composition and biological properties of Indian propolis. The study on Indian propolis has just started and only a few reports are available in the literature on the chemical composition and its beneficial as well as pharmacological properties. Earlier, we have reported the wound healing and anti-ulcerogenic properties of Indian propolis in experimental animal models. The acute oral toxicity conducted in experimental rats revealed the non-toxic nature of the propolis. Several reports are available in the literature describing the effect of seasonality on biological activity of propolis extract [42].

The present study is aimed to determine the effect of seasonal variation on the levels of flavonoid and phenolic content and the anti-oxidant potential of the propolis collected three times during the year 2024, in the spring (April to June), summer (July to September) and fall (October to December) covering over a period of one year.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Propolis samples and preparation of extract

The raw propolis samples were collected three times during the year 2024 (spring, summer and fall) and samples were harvested from the same apiary located in the protected area near Mudivaithaanendal, Vakaikulam, Thoothukudi District, Tamil Nadu, India using propolis traps and they were stored in the dark at 0°C until their processing. The samples were collected in the middle of May, August and November 2024. The frozen samples were cut into small pieces, weighed and extracted with 10-fold volume of ethanol (95% v/v) under constant stirring overnight and centrifuged at 27000 rpm for 15mins [43]. The supernatant was then concentrated until constant weight in a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure at 0°C . The residues were dissolved in DMSO for antioxidant assays and in methanol for the analysis of chemical composition. All other chemicals, solvents, and reagents procured for conducting the present study were of analytical grade obtained from SRL, Mumbai.

Phytochemical screening

The ethanolic extract of propolis was subjected to phytochemical screening for the qualitative analysis of phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, pectins, tannins, phytosterols, triterpenoids, anthraquinones, and phenols [44, 45]. The experiments were conducted in triplicates to obtain concordant data.

Determination of total phenolic content

Total phenolic content in the ethanol extract of propolis was determined according to the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric method [46, 47]. A standard curve was drawn with gallic acid reference solutions. In brief, 2 to 10 ml of standard aqueous gallic acid solution (100 μ g/ml) was pipetted into a 100 ml volumetric flask containing 70 ml of distilled water. Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (5 ml) and 10 ml of saturated sodium bicarbonate solution were added, and the total volume was made up to 100 ml with distilled water. The solution was thoroughly mixed. The blank was prepared in the same manner but without gallic acid. After 1 h of incubation at room temperature, the absorbance was measured at 760 nm. The samples were prepared in triplicates for each analysis, and the mean value was calculated. For the determination of total phenolic content in the propolis extract, aqueous solutions at the final concentration of 20 μ g/ml were used; proceeding in the same manner described for the reference solutions, and the total phenolic content was expressed as mg per gram of gallic acid equivalents.

Determination of total flavonoid content

Total flavonoid content in the ethanolic extract of propolis was determined according to the method of Quettier-Deleu et al. (2000) with minor modifications [48]. A standard curve was built with quercetin reference solutions. 2 to 8 ml of standard quercetin (50 μ g/ml) were pipetted into 25 ml volumetric flasks containing 1 ml of 2% aluminium chloride dissolved in ethanol, and the total volume was made up to 25 ml with ethanol. The blank was prepared by diluting 1 ml of 2% aluminium chloride dissolved in ethanol in a 25 ml volumetric flask with ethanol. After 1 hour of incubation at room temperature, the absorbance was measured at 420 nm. Propolis extracts were prepared at a final concentration of 20 μ g/ml proceeding in the same manner described for the reference solutions and the total flavonoid content was calculated as quercetin equivalents from a calibration curve. The experiments were performed in triplicate for each analysis, and the mean value of absorbance was recorded to determine the total flavonoid content in the propolis extract.

Free radical scavenging assays

DPPH (1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging assay

The free radical scavenging capacity of the ethanolic extract of propolis extract was determined using DPPH radical [49]. DPPH (200 μM) solution was prepared in 95% methanol. From the stock, propolis extract solution was prepared in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ Tris HCl buffer (pH 7.9). 200, 400, 600, 800, and 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were taken in five test tubes. 0.5 ml of freshly prepared DPPH solution was incubated with fruits extracts and kept under light protection for 20 min at room temperature. The decrease of absorbance at 517 nm was measured using the spectrophotometer. Deionised water was used as a blank experiment, and standard ascorbic acid was used as a positive control. The assay was performed in triplicate, and the mean value of absorbance was calculated.

% scavenging activity = $\frac{\text{Absorbance of the Blank} - \text{Absorbance of the sample}}{\text{Absorbance of the blank}} \times 100$

Absorbance of the blank X 100

ABTS^{•+} (2, 2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) radical cation scavenging assay

ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity of ethanolic extract of propolis extract was determined according to the method of Re *et al.*, 1999 [50]. Briefly, ABTS radical cation (ABTS^{•+}) in 20 mmol sodium acetate buffer (pH-4.5) was combined with 2.45 mmol potassium per sulfate to generate a stable dark blue-green radical following 12-16 h of incubation at 4 °C in the dark. The reaction mixture is suitably diluted to an absorbance of 0.7 \pm 0.01 at 734 nm spectrophotometrically to obtain the test reagent. The reaction mixture containing different concentrations (200-1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of propolis extract and 3.0 ml of test reagent was incubated in a water bath at 30 °C for 30 min. The test solution mixture turns colorless, and the absorbance is reduced due to the sequestration of unpaired electrons in the test reagent by the antioxidants present in the propolis extract. Standard ascorbic acid was used as a reference to compare the antioxidant potential of the propolis extract. The antioxidant assay was performed in triplicate, and the mean value of absorbance obtained was calculated.

Assay for Nitric oxide (NO) scavenging activity

Sodium nitroprusside (5 mmol) in phosphate buffer (pH 7.7) was incubated with 200, 400, 600, 800, and 1000 µg/ml concentrations of propolis extract dissolved in a suitable solvent (alcohol), and tubes were incubated at 25 °C for two hours. At intervals, 0.5 ml of incubation solution was removed and diluted with 0.5 ml of Griess reagent. The assay was performed in triplicate, and the mean value of absorbance was calculated. The absorbance of the chromophore formed during the diazotization of nitrite with sulfanilamide and subsequent N-naphthyl ethylenediamine was measured at 546 nm. Standard ascorbic acid was used as a reference to compare the nitric oxide scavenging activity of the propolis extract [51].

Superoxide anion (SO) radical scavenging assay

The superoxide radical scavenging activity of propolis extract was measured by the method of Fontana et al. (2001) [52]. The method is based on the generation of superoxide radical by auto-oxidation of riboflavin in the presence of light. In this method, the free radical scavenging activity is measured by reduction of riboflavin/light/NBT (nitro blue tetrazolium salt). The 1 ml of reaction mixture contained phosphate buffer, NADH, NBT, and various concentrations of the sample solution. The superoxide radical reduces NBT to a blue-colored Formazon that can be measured spectrophotometrically at 560 nm. Standard ascorbic acid was used as a reference to compare the efficacy. The experiments were performed in triplicate, and the mean value of absorbance was calculated.

Statistical analysis

All the data obtained were grouped and statistically evaluated with the aid of SPSS 16.0 software. Hypothesis testing method included one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by post hoc testing performed with least significance difference (LSD). The value of $P < 0.05$ was considered to indicate statistical significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ethanol extract of the propolis was filtered, dried, and weighed. The yield was around 8.5% w/w. Table 1 shows the data obtained through qualitative analysis of phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, tannins, pectins, phytosterols, triterpenoids, phenols, and anthraquinones in the propolis extract of all the samples. Phytochemicals are ecologically derived, non-nutrient, bioactive compounds synthesized by the plants to protect themselves from environmental stress such as high temperature, extreme cold and microbial

assaults. However, the phyto-ingredients possess the ability to exercise pharmacological as well as several beneficial effects on human health. The phytochemical screening forms the basis for the quantitative estimation of bioactive constituents present in various parts of natural products. The qualitative analysis of the propolis evidenced the presence of several important bioactive principles, such as phenolic and flavonoids, which readily accounts for their folklore medicinal claims.

Table 1: Qualitative phytochemical screening of propolis extract

PHYTOCHEMICALS	Season		
	Spring	Summer	Fall
Alkaloids	+	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+	+
Glycosides	+	+	+
Saponins	+	+	+
Tannins	+	+	+
Pectins	+	+	+
Anthraquinones	-	-	-
Phytosterols	+	+	+
Triterpenoids	-	-	-
Phenols	+	+	+

The results obtained are in accordance with the earlier reports on propolis [53-57]. The propolis is a rich source of pectins, which have a high potential for use in food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries [58]. Pectin is one of the major components of terrestrial plants. Pectins are water-soluble hetero polysaccharides known to control the pore size of the plant cell wall, regulating cell-cell adhesion and providing a source of signaling molecules that elicit a wide range of cellular responses. Pectins are capable of holding water and forming gel, which

property eventually leads to the binding of ions and bile acids. Low toxicity, availability, accessibility, and affordability enable the pectin to occupy a significant position in the biomedical and pharmacological arena, such as anti-cholesterolemic, improving insulin resistance, anti-hyperglycemic, antioxidant, anti-constipating, and powerful prebiotic substrates [59-62]. Pectin is an outstanding component for bio-ink formulation as it has exceptional biocompatibility and efficiently combines with other biomaterials. Above all, pectins are widely used as an adsorbent, emulsion stabilizer, and coating material for tablets, pellets, micro particles, and beads [63-65]. However, the yield and quantity of the pectins vary greatly depending on the plant source.

Similarly, polyphenols are a large family of naturally occurring phytochemicals found in many plants. They are broadly classified into four groups. Flavonoids account for nearly 60% of total polyphenols present in plants, which chiefly include quercetin, kaempferol, catechins, and anthocyanins. The second class of phenolic acids accounts for around 30% of all polyphenols, and the examples include ferulic acid and chlorogenic acids. The other minor groups include polyphenolic amides (avenanthramides and capsaicinoids) and stilbenes (resveratrol), tannic acids, and lignins. Polyphenols are responsible for antioxidant, antimicrobial, and prebiotic-like effects on gut microbiota and inflammatory stress. Historically, polyphenols are used as dyes and in tanning industries. The polyphenolic content of the propolis is responsible for the bitterness and astringency [66]. Thus, the presence of polyphenols in the propolis provides evidence for their beneficial and pharmacological actions in the folklore medicinal system.

Alkaloids are specialized organic secondary molecules gifted with numerous biological properties. The presence of alkaloids in the propolis extract is of important significance in terms of its pharmacological and beneficial effects. Alkaloids constitute an important class of structurally diversified compounds that have a nitrogen atom in their heterocyclic ring and are derived from amino acids. Alkaloids form about 20% of plant-derived secondary metabolites. The notable examples of alkaloids include paclitaxel, morphine, codeine, nicotine, vincristine, caffeine, atropine, papaverine, thebaine, vasicine, strychnine, brucine, etc. [67]. Traditional and modern health care systems have harnessed the potential of alkaloids for the treatment of several human ailments, such as antibiotics, antimicrobials, anti-inflammatory, anticancer agents, and different degenerative diseases. Paracetamol, an alkaloid, is widely prescribed for fast pain relief of headaches, backaches, rheumatic and muscle pain, fever, and pains due to cold and flu. Due to

their immense pharmacological properties, alkaloids are in great demand for pharmaceutical formulations, especially for the lethal diseases such as cancer and inflammatory disorders. Several synthetic and semi synthetic drugs are structural modifications of the alkaloids, which were designed to modulate the primary effect of the drugs to reduce the undesirable side effects [68, 69].

The term “tannin” was originally coined by Seguin to describe the substances present in plant extracts capable of converting animal skin into leather [70, 71]. They are complex chemical substances derived from phenolic acids and are responsible for the astringency, color, and flavor. Tannins are water soluble and contain a large number of hydroxyl or other functional groups. The best examples of tannins include tannic acid, ellagic acid, chlorogenic acid, quercetin, rutin, apigenin, kaempferol, and luteolin. Tannins are present in varying concentrations in plants, and their presence in the propolis extract forms the basis for its medicinal value. Tannins are important plant secondary metabolites with anticarcinogenic [72] antimutagenic, anti-lipidemic [73], acceleration of blood clotting [74] and control of blood pressure [75] properties. During ripening of tannin-containing fruits, tannic acid is hydrolyzed to gallic acid or ellagic acid, which in turn elicits profound antimicrobial activity [76]. The anti-nutritional and pharmacological effects of dietary tannins and their interactions with enzymes and other proteins have been extensively reported [77-82]. The antioxidant and other pharmacological activity of tannins are mainly due to the presence of hydroxyl and other functional groups present in them. However, tannins are often referred to as a double-edged sword, as their consumption at large levels may lead to unpleasant health complications.

Flavonoids are an important group of plant-derived secondary metabolites, which essentially consist of a benzopyrone ring bearing a phenolic or polyphenolic group at different positions [83]. However, the therapeutic efficacy of the flavonoids is essentially associated with the molecular structure and, more precisely, with the location and total number of the –OH groups present. So far, over 10,000 flavonoids have been isolated and identified, and most of them are widely accepted as therapeutic agents [84, 85]. Flavonoids are sub-divided into flavanones, flavanols, flavans, Chalcones, isoflavonoids, and anthocyanidins based on their chemical structure, degree of unsaturation, and oxidation of carbon ring. The well-established flavonoids widely used in the treatment of various human ailments include Hesperidin [86], Aurone [87], Quercetin [88], Luteolin [89], Kaempferol [90], Myricetin [91], Silibinin [92],

Morin [93], Rutin [94], and Chrysin[95]. Flavonoids have been reported to elicit anticancer [96], anti-microbial [97, 98], anti-tumour [99], anti-hypertensive [100-103, anti-oxidant [104,105] and cardio-protective [106] properties.

Saponins are a structurally and biologically diverse class of plant secondary metabolites that are widely distributed in terrestrial plants and intimately involved in our daily lives. Saponins are characterized by one or more hydrophilic glycosides combined with a lipophilic triterpene or steroid molecule such as an aglycone. The structural diversity of saponins lies mainly in their sugar moieties [107-109].

Table 2 represents the total phenolic and flavonoid contents in the propolis extract. It was found that the total phenolic and flavonoid content was relatively higher in samples collected during the summer. Phenols are very important plant constituents because of their free radical scavenging ability, which is in turn due to the presence of hydroxyl groups in them [110]. Similarly, flavonoids are an important group of polyphenols widely distributed among the plant flora and containing a benzopyrone that is used as antioxidants or free radical scavengers [111]. The significant levels of total phenolic and flavonoid contents provide further evidence for the presence of biologically active phytoingredients in the ethanolic extract of propolis.

Table 2: Total flavonoid and phenolic content of propolis extract

CONSTITUENTS	Season		
	Spring	Summer	Fall
Phenolic content milligrams of gallic acid equivalents per gram of methanolic extract.	61.65±.03	74.45±.05	58.40±.06
Flavonoid content milligrams of quercetin equivalents per gram of methanolic extract.	9.65±0.4	14.85±0.3	8.60±0.5

Several methods have been introduced to estimate the antioxidant potential of biological and plant-derived phytochemicals. The perception of antioxidant capacity was originated from chemistry and subsequently to biology, epidemiology, and nutrition [112-114]. The antioxidant assays describe the ability of redox molecules in foods and biological systems to scavenge free radicals. This concept provides a broader spectrum of the antioxidants present in a sample as it considers the additive and synergistic effects of all antioxidants rather than the effect of individual compounds and may, therefore, be useful to evaluate the potential health benefits of antioxidants on oxidative stress-mediated human ailments [115,116]. In recent years, a wide range of spectrophotometric assays have been assumed to assay the antioxidant potential of several compounds, the most accepted being 2,2'-azino-bis-3-ethylbenzthiazoline-6-sulphonic acid (ABTS) and 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assays. Both assays employ the same principle: a synthetic colored radical or redox-active compound is generated, and the efficacy of the biological sample to scavenge the radical or to reduce the redox-active compound is monitored spectrophotometrically. Appropriate standards have been used to quantify the antioxidant capacity of the samples.

The *in vitro* DPPH and ABTS radicals scavenging activity of propolis extract was presented in figs. 1 and 2, respectively. The propolis extract scavenges the DPPH free radicals in a dose-dependent manner. The percentage inhibition ranges from 35 to 70% at a concentration range of 200-1000 µg/ml. Similarly, the percentage of inhibition of ABTS radicals was found to be in the range of 40 to 75.5%. Among the several *in vitro* antioxidant assays, DPPH* and ABTS*⁺ assays have been widely used as more reliable methods in determining the free radical scavenging efficacy of unknown compounds [117,118]. The antiradical activity assay is based on the reduction of DPPH* in methanolic solution. Due to the presence of an odd electron, DPPH gives a strong absorption maximum at 517 nm. As this electron becomes paired off in the presence of a hydrogen donor, i.e., a free radical scavenging antioxidant, the absorption strength is decreased, and the resulting decolorization is stoichiometric with respect to the number of electrons captured. It has been found that DPPH* can oxidise cysteine, glutathione, ascorbic acid, tocopherol, and polyhydroxy aromatic compounds [119].

Fig. 1: DPPH radical scavenging assay of ethanolic extract of propolis.

(The values are expressed as mean \pm SD; n=3).

Fig. 2: ABTS radical scavenging assay of ethanolic extract of propolis.

The values are expressed as mean \pm SD; n=3

ABTS^{*+} produces more powerful free radicals than DPPH* radicals and the reactions with ABTS^{*+} radicals involve a single electron transfer process [120]. The principle of the ABTS^{*+} assay is that the preformed radical monocation of ABTS^{*+} is generated by oxidation of ABTS^{*+} with potassium persulfate and is reduced in the presence of such hydrogen-donating antioxidants.

The nitric oxide scavenging activity (fig. 3) of the fruits extract ranges from 45 to 76%, whereas the superoxide radical scavenging activity (fig. 4) ranges from 43 to 83%. Nitric oxide radicals are derived from the interaction of NO with oxygen or reactive oxygen species. NO is a diffusible free radical that plays many roles as an effectors molecule in diverse biological systems, including neuronal messenger, vasodilatation, and antimicrobial and antitumor activities [121]. Chronic exposure to nitric oxide radical is associated with various carcinomas and inflammatory conditions, including juvenile diabetes, multiple sclerosis, arthritis, and ulcerative colitis. The toxicity of NO increases greatly when it reacts with the superoxide radical, forming the highly reactive peroxynitrite anion (ONOO⁻). Nitric oxide has been shown to be directly scavenged by flavonoids [122].

Fig. 3: Nitric oxide scavenging assay of ethanolic extract of propolis.

(The values are expressed as mean±SD; n=3).

Nitric oxide radical Scavenging potential of Propolis extract in various seasons

Fig.4: Superoxide radical scavenging assay of ethanolic extract of Propolis.(The values are expressed as mean \pm SD; n=3).***Superoxide scavenging potential of Propolis extract in various seasons***

In vitro quenching of NO radical is one of the methods that can be used to determine antioxidant activity [123]. The procedure is based on the principle that sodium nitroprusside in aqueous solution at physiological pH spontaneously generates nitric oxide, which interacts with oxygen to produce nitrite ions that can be estimated using the Griess reagent. Scavengers of nitric oxide compete with oxygen, leading to reduced production of nitrite ions [124].

Superoxides are formed from molecular oxygen by oxidative enzymes as well as via non-enzymatic reactions such as auto-oxidation by catecholamines [125]. It is extremely harmful to cellular components. Superoxide anions play an important role in the formation of other reactive oxygen species such as hydrogen peroxide, hydroxyl radical, and singlet oxygen, which readily induce oxidative damage in lipids, protein, and DNA [126].

Superoxide, which is an anion radical, is produced by the one-electron reduction of molecular oxygen. In aqueous media, protonation of superoxide can form the uncharged hydroperoxyl radical (HOO•), which exhibits a pKa of 4.8, meaning that the anion radical form

is by far the predominant species at physiological pH ranges. A second reduction of superoxide would require the energetically disfavored compression of two full negative charges on a diatomic molecule. As a result, superoxide is generally a better reducing agent than the oxidising agent. In addition, superoxide does not cross lipid membranes readily. Superoxide is relatively unreactive toward most biological molecules, although the low levels of superoxide permitted in cells and tissues indicate that limiting cell exposures to superoxide is a significant selector for survival. The levels of superoxide are kept low by effective compartmentalization of the sequential reductions of oxygen and by extensive expressions of superoxide dismutases with high affinities for superoxide [127,128]. The observed significant *in vitro* antioxidant properties of the propolis extract may be due to the increased levels of phenolic and flavonoids present in them [129].

CONCLUSION

A thorough literature survey revealed that the reports involving the phytochemical screening and pharmacological properties of propolis are sparse. The results of the present study evidenced the presence of pharmacologically active phytochemicals in the ethanolic extract of propolis. The total phenolic and flavonoid contents readily account for the *in vitro* free radical scavenging activity of the propolis extract. Thus, it can be concluded that the propolis extract may be considered as a rich source for the identification of nutraceuticals with diversified medicinal values. From the data obtained, it can also be concluded that the propolis extract may be considered a potential source of antioxidants. Above all, the total phenolic and flavonoid content of propolis extract was found to be relatively higher in samples collected during summer and consequently the free radical scavenging capacity was also found to be increased in the sample.

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